

PREPOTENCY OF NEEDS AND REWARD VALENCE OF EMPLOYEES IN MINISTRY OF EAST AFRICAN COMMUNITY AFFAIRS IN UGANDA

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Citation: Oluka, B.B. (2020). Prepotency of Needs and Reward Valence of Employees in Ministry Of East African Community Affairs in Uganda. *KIU Interdisciplinary Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences*, 1(1), 16-27

ABSTRACT

The study analyzed the prepotency of needs and reward valence of employees in the Ministry of East African Community Affairs. Specifically, the study aimed at determining the influence of Maslow's hierarchy of needs, that is; physiological needs, safety needs, belonging needs esteem-needs and self –actualization needs on reward valence of the employees of the Ministry of East African Community Affairs in Uganda, comparing if there was a significant difference between male and female respondents as to: extent of prepotency of needs and level of reward valence; and establishing if there was a significant relationship between prepotency of needs and level of reward valence. Standardized - Self-Administered Questionnaires by Reasoner (1976) (SAQs) together with a Research Devised Questionnaire were utilized for data collection. The study revealed that there was influence of; physiological needs, safety needs, belonging needs esteem needs and self-actualization on reward valence was satisfactorily meant for both the male and female respondents. From the findings, the researcher concluded that the employees, physiological needs, safety needs, belonging needs, esteem needs and self – actualization needs were fairly met in the Ministry of East African Community Affairs of Uganda. The researcher recommended that the government should set up policies and guidelines to identify and meet the needs of employees; find ways of rewarding employees by enhancing their salaries, allowances and other motivational strategies. All these should be gender sensitive.

Keywords: Prepotency of needs; reward valence; hierarchy of needs; Abraham Maslow

INTRODUCTION

The public service in Uganda was once described as the best in service in Africa south of the Sahara. Of recent, it has been characterised by lower work performance, poor service delivery, indicated by absenteeism, lateness, corruption and low-quality output. This is in spite of the high-quality staff it has (Byarugaba, 1978). One has to ask what happened. This potential of high performance is stifled by inability of the

hitherto civil service reforms to fully integrate prepotency of needs and reward valence. Our effort will have a significant positive impact on the civil service motivation leading to high performance. It is an attempt to diagnose what went wrong and arrive to a prescription.

The interactions between the civil service and the private sector in Africa, as elsewhere, are complex. The nature of the relationship between the two varies with a country’s history, economic policies and political orientation. Even so, it is possible to identify some common threads of experience that have defined the relationship between the two sectors in Africa. The commonly observed pattern of state activism in all African countries in the first two decades of post-independence meant that nationalism, rather than socialist ideology, was the dominant influence. Nationalism supplied the impetus for the Africanisation of the civil service. And nationalism also inspired the nationalization or indigenization of foreign enterprises that dominated the private sector in several African countries at independence. Now, it is economic reforms that are re-defining the relationship between both sectors.

The effects of nationalist orientation were manifest in several ways. For example, before the onset of the economic crisis in the mid-eighties, the civil service witnessed a phenomenal growth in size. By contrast; the private sector virtually atrophied or, in any case, was not the “dynamic’ sector, after allowing for the fact that agriculture in many African countries remained in private, mostly rural hands. It is, therefore, not surprising that, during this period, there was an uneasy relationship between the civil service and the private sector for several reasons. First, the exuberance of nationalism cast the private sector as agents of imperialism and the civil service as an embodiment of patriotism: Second, as the growth of the civil service led to a fall in the quality of its services, the efficiency of the private sector suffered as well. Third, the civil service was used to push the nostrum of government into areas that should have been left to the private sector. This particular action bred competition between both sectors and fueled the “conflict” between the civil service and the private sector.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Conceptual frame work

This could be shown farther by using Potters Model as an explanatory tool.

Adopted from: Motivation Model (Porter and Lawler-1968: 75).

Armstrong and Stephens (2005:74) have stated that motivation is likely only when a clearly perceived usable relationship exists between performance and outcome, and the outcome is seen as a means of satisfying needs this explains why extrinsic financial motivation-for example, an incentive or bonus scheme – works only if the link between effort and reward is understood (there is a clear ‘line of sight’) and the value of the reward is worth the effort. It also explains why intrinsic motivation arising from the work itself can be more powerful than extrinsic motivation. Intrinsic motivation outcomes are more under the control of individuals, who can judge from past experience the extent to which advantageous results are likely to be obtained by their behavior.

This theory was developed by Porter and Lawler (1968) into a model which follows Vroom’s ideas by suggesting that there are two factors determining the effort people put into their jobs (1) the value of the reward to individuals in so far as they satisfy their need for security, social esteem, autonomy and self-actualization (2) the probability that reward depends on efforts, as perceived by individuals – in other words, their expectations of the relationship between effort and reward. Thus, the greater the value of a set of rewards the higher the probability that receiving each of these rewards depends on effort, the greater the effort that will be made in a given situation. But as Porter and Lawler emphasize, mere effort is not enough. It has to be effective effort if it is to produce the desired performance. The two variables additional to effort which affect task achievement are (1) ability-individual characteristics such as intelligence, manual skills, know-how (2) role perceptions-what individuals want to do or think they are required to do. They are good from the point of view of the organization if they correspond with what it thinks the individual ought to be doing. They are poor if the views of the individual and the organization do not coincide.

Maslow's hierarchy of needs theory states that an individual has a hierarchy of motivational needs (Maslow, 1954); the most basic needs are physiological, including the need for food and sleep. The next level is safety needs, including security and stability needs. In level three, we find needs of belonging and love that are also termed social needs, including love, be loved, and a sense of belonging. In level four, we find the needs for self-esteem, including achievements, respect and recognition from others. Finally, Maslow believes that in the highest level of needs are self-actualization needs, which refer to people's aspirations to achieve self-fulfillment and realize their potential. Sheldon et al. (2001) reviewed Maslow's hierarchy of needs theory and related research and proposed that pleasure-stimulation is one of the ten most basic human needs.

Happiness is achieved through the pursuit of pleasure, enjoyment, and comfort in the hedonic view and through seeking to use or develop the best in oneself in the eudemonic view (Huta & Ryan, 2010). Moreover, eudemonia also refers to the feeling of moving toward self-realization (Waterman et al., 2008) and is similar to self-actualization associated with more-frequent peak experiences (Huta & Ryan, 2010). However, all these theories provide vital related studies but did not find out the extent of the prepotency of needs and reward valence among employees in the public sector of Uganda.

Theoretical Perspective

Theoretically this study is based on the theory of Abraham Maslow's hierarchy of needs that states that we must satisfy each need in turn, starting with the first, which deals with the most obvious needs for survival itself. Only when the lower order needs of physical and emotional wellbeing are satisfied, are we concerned with the higher order needs of influence and personal development. Conversely, if the things that satisfy our lower order needs are swept away, we are no longer concerned about the maintenance of our higher order needs (Cole, 2004:36).

The study was anchored on Maslow's theory of hierarchy of needs that is the prepotency of needs, which is operationalized as; physiological needs, safety needs, belonging needs, esteem needs, self-actualization needs and reward valence which has 16 items which are; the value of the rewards positively affects the employees to satisfy their needs for security, each individual in the ministry thinks that the value of a reward meets the need for some esteem, the need for autonomy is necessarily satisfied by the value of the reward, supervision should aim at having employees' needs met by the value of the rewards as regards the effort that the employees put on the job, the value of the reward depends upon the effort perceived by an individual in the ministry, many employees' expectations on reward should be commensurate with their efforts, the individual in the ministry perceives the value of a reward in terms of effective effort if it is to produce the desired performance, the realization of the value of a reward depends entirely on the effort of the individual at

work, the value of the reward is closely associated with the organization's or ministry's expectations of employees work, employees must be rewarded if they perform beyond the ministry's expectations, organizational structure positively affects the reward valence, organizational systems positively affect the reward valence, organizational processes positively affect the rewarding systems, incentive and bonuses would improve the performance of employees and management makes judgments for salary increases, promotions, transfers and sometimes demotions or terminations. These variables the independent and dependent variables are meant to study and examine the effects of the employees of the East African Community Affairs.

Prepotency of needs/hierarchy of needs

These are motivational needs of the employees of the Ministry of East African Community Affairs under the study. In this study, the prepotency of needs is categorized as follows: physiological needs, safety needs, belonging needs, esteem needs and self-actualization needs Koontz and Weirich (1988:416). The researcher analyzed these needs as they concern the employees of the Ministry of East African Community Affairs in Uganda.

With the high number of employees, the Ministry of East African Community Affairs with 67 employees (30 males and 37 females) recruited and appointed by the government of Uganda to carry out their activities, it seems to suggest that the government of Uganda is committed to delivering results. The ministry of East African Community Affairs has got employees that deal with regional issues. These are the reasons why the researcher selected them to participate in the study.

Reward valence

Shields (2007) in discussing rewarding employee performance cite McAdam (1999) who defined "recognition plans" as those that "honor outstanding performance after the fact and are designed for awareness, role modeling, and retention of recipients." McAdams (1999) cited by Shields (2007) affirmed to this study when he distinguished between recognition plans and performance improvement plans in that the former are retrospective and generally discretionary in nature, whereas, the latter are formula driven and specify both performance expectation, targets or goals and potential reward outcomes in advance of actual performance.

Recognition for immediate past performance may involve rewards that are either financial or nonfinancial in nature. However, the cash and non-cash approaches are by no means mutually exclusive and frequently go hand in hand in a (total reward management approach). He recognized that awards can be categorized according to six main dimensions; the frequency with which rewards are given (day to day, weekly, monthly, quarterly, yearly); whether recipients are individuals or groups; how award recipients are determined (by supervisors, peer nomination, or customers); the performance criteria (membership behavior, task behavior, organizational citizenship behavior, results); The fifth main dimension of recognition

is the degree of plan formality and structure, Informal plans include ad hoc awards issued at the discretion of the supervisor; more formal or structured plan include employee of the month awards that cascade through to “employee of the year” ceremonies. The sixth dimension is the form that the award takes (cash, none cash or combined cash and none cash).

He added that, while many recognition plans are based on supervisory assessment of employee excellence in many cases decisions about award recipients are made by peers. Peers are said to invest awards with greater credibility and reward valence. Peer nomination also allows employers to side step the need to find objective criteria for measuring employee performance.

Recognition should be both celebratory and fun; if one can reward a person and have fun in the process, one will satisfy two important desires of most employees; to be appreciated for the work they do and to enjoy their jobs and work place. The “Rewards and Recognition” scheme may include a “Thank You Note” (leading to cash prizes) Cash best ‘achiever of the year awards’ “Great Performance Award”, “Chairman’s Award for Quality” and international “Great Performance Grand Award” (Shields, 1994). McAdam affirmed to this study when he discussed the reward management approach.

The Porter and Lawler Model, (1968) cited in Armstrong and Stephens 2005:pg. 69-83) indicated that the amount of effort (the strength of motivation and energy exerted) depends on the value of a reward (plus the amount of energy exerted) plus the amount of energy a person believes is required and the probability of receiving the reward. Essentially, it proposes that a reward system will promote desired task behavior where; it offers valued rewards commensurate with the effort required, and it establishes a clear and achievable pathway between effort and reward (Shields, 2007).

The perceived effort and probability of actually getting a reward are in turn also are influenced by the record of actual performance. Clearly, if people know they can do a job or if they have done it they have a better appreciation of the effort required and know better the probability of rewards. Actual performance in a job (the doing of tasks or the meeting of goals) is determined principally by effort expended. But it is also greatly, influenced by an individual’s ability (knowledge and skills) to do the job and by his or her perception of what the required task is (the extent to which the person understands the goals; required activities and other elements of a task.

Performance in turn, is seen as leading to intrinsic rewards (such as working conditions and status). Those rewards tempered by what the individual sees as equitable and believe in satisfaction. But performance also influences sensed equitable rewards. What the individual sees as a fair reward for effort will not necessarily affect the satisfaction derived. Likewise, the actual value of rewards will be influenced by satisfaction. In the theory, Porter (1968) meant that managers

should have their reward structures and that through careful planning; managing by objectives and clear definition of duties and responsibilities by good organization structuring the effort performance- reward satisfaction system can be integrated into an entire system management.

An important factor in the motivation is whether individuals perceive the reward structures as being fair. Equity theory refers to the individuals' subjective judgments about the equity or fairness of reward they got in relationship to the inputs (which include many factors such as effort, experience, education, and so on) in comparison with others. Adams (1999) has received a great deal of credit for the formulation of the equity (or inequity) theory the essential aspects of the equity theory may be shown as:

$$\frac{\text{Outcomes by a person}}{\text{Inputs by a person}} = \frac{\text{outcomes by another person}}{\text{inputs by another person}}$$

There should be a balance of the outcomes /inputs relationship for one person in comparison with another person. This is reflected in the study of the Ministry of East African Community Affairs both public and private. The study sought to prove this hypothesis. If people feel they are inadequately rewarded, reduce the quality of or quantity of input or leave the organization. If people perceive rewards, as equitable, they probably will continue at the same level of output. If people think that the rewards are greater than what is considered equitable, they may work harder. It is also possible that some may discount the reward. One of the problems is that people may over estimate their own contributions and the rewards others receive.

Developed by Psychologist B.F. Skinner (1988) is called Positive Reinforcement Behavior Modification, this holds that individuals can be motivated by proper design of their work equivalent for poor performance modulates negative results. Specific goals are not then set with winners' participation and assistance, prompt and regular feedback of results is made available and performance improvements are rewarded with recognition and praise. Even when performance does not equal goals, ways are found to help people and praise them for the good things they do. It emphasizes the removal of obstructions to performance, careful planning and organizing control through feedback and the expansion of communication. However, these theories fall short of not having investigated the prepotency and reward valence of employees in Uganda public service which this study intended to do.

RESEARCH HYPOTHESES

To this end the study proposed these null hypotheses:

Ho#1: There is no significant difference between the prepotency of needs and reward valence of employees of the Ministry of East African Community Affairs.

Ho#2: There is no significant relationship between prepotency of needs and reward valence of the employees of the Ministry of East African Community Affairs.

METHODOLOGY

The study used descriptive correlations survey used during the study mainly because the researcher was interested in the determination of whether or not and to what extent an association existed between physiological needs, safety needs, belonging needs, esteem needs, self-actualization needs and reward valence were correlated. The two variables, the prepotency of needs which were operationalized as Maslow's hierarchy of needs and reward valence where itemized as quantifiable variables to determine how they are affected the employees in Ministry of East African Community Affairs. These were investigated by having a literature study, which was undertaken to identify motivational needs, Maslow's hierarchy of needs and reward valence.

The study utilized the Likert scale which consisted of the response modes of strongly agree, agree, neutral, disagree, and strongly disagree. An empirical research study consisting of a survey was conducted using two questionnaires:

1. The Standardized Questionnaires on prepotency of needs which was adopted from Reasoner (1976), which consisted of twenty (20) items referring to physiological needs (items 1,4,16,20), safety needs (items 2,3,9,19), belonging needs (items 5,7,12,17), esteem needs (items 6,8 and 17) and self-actualization needs (items 10,11,13 and 18). The response modes were strongly-agree (4), agree (3), disagree (2) and strongly disagree (1).
2. A Researcher Devised Questionnaire to determine the level of reward valence was used. This questionnaire had sixteen items with respond modes and scoring system similar to the standardized questionnaires on the influence of physiological needs, safety needs, belonging needs, esteem needs and actualization needs. The researcher collected data from two quantifiable variables from the same group of subjects that is the employees of Ministry of East African Community Affairs and then compared how they varied.

The purpose of this research design was to compare two or more characteristics from the same group, to explain how characteristics vary together and to predict one variable from the other. The justification was to provide rigorous and replicable procedure for understanding relationships and to determine whether and to what degree these relationships existed between two quantifiable variables (Oso and Onen 2008:71). The interest here was to explore the relationship between the prepotency of needs and reward valence among the employees of Ministry of East African

Community Affairs. Within this design, the descriptive comparative and correlation were also used to describe significant differences, and the cause and effect relationship respectively.

Validity of the Instruments

Validity is the ability to produce findings that are in alignment with theoretical or conceptual values, in other words to produce accurate results and to measure what is supposed to be measured. The two instruments measured what they were supposed to measure and thus the data collected honestly and accurately represent the respondents' opinions.

Furthermore, construct validity and factor analysis was ensured for the questionnaires and Cronbach alpha to test for the reliability of the research questionnaires. While the Standardized Questionnaires were selected to measure the extent of prepotency of needs and the information that was obtained served the purpose of the study. The validity of these questionnaires produced findings that were in agreement with the theoretical perspective, produced accurate results and measured what they were supposed to measure that is; the influence of psychological needs, belonging needs, safety needs, esteem needs, and self-actualization needs on the reward valence. The Research Devised Questionnaire also measured the reward valence as it was expected and was in line with the variable to be measured. This instrument consistently measured the reward valence of the respondents in the study. Hence the consistency shown as the dependent variable was measured. The validity of the two instruments was checked by the empirical validation and theoretical validation whereas the empirical validation was checked by the validity of the questionnaires against empirical evidence. Based on the theoretical validation the validity of the instruments was ascertained through theoretical and conceptual constructs. In both cases validity was upheld by the findings produced through the measures in question and supported by empirical evidence and theoretical principles.

The Content Validity

The content validity focused on the extent to which the content of the instruments corresponded to the content of the theoretical concept it was designed to measure. The content validity involved specifying the domain of the content for the concepts, constructing and selecting the indicator that represented that domain of content (Amin 2004:286) of which the coefficient of validity was measured as $CVI = (\text{number of items declared valid} / (\text{total number of items})) = 236/567 = 0.416$.

Construct validity focused on the assessment of whether a particular measure related to other measures consistent with the theoretical perspective and derived the hypotheses concerning the relationships among the two variables and concepts. Cronbach (1946) observed that, "construct validation takes place when an investigator believes his instrument reflects a particular construct to which are

attached to certain meanings. The proposed interpretation generated specific hypothesis, which are a means of confirming or disconfirming the claim “thus necessity construct validity is assessed within a given theoretical context (Amin 2004:289).

TEST OF HYPOTHESES

Ho1: There is no significant difference between the prepotency of needs and reward valence among the employees of Ministry of East African Community Affairs

Table 1: ANOVA Table (Level of significance 0.05)

	Sum of squares	Degrees of freedom	Mean square	F Statistic	Sig.
	19.402	43	.451		0.000
	27.612	191	.145		
Total	47.014	234			

Using the Analysis of Variance to establish whether there is no significant difference between the Prepotency of Needs and the Level of Reward Valence among employees of Ministry of East African Community Affairs, the results reveal a significant difference between the prepotency of needs and the reward valence (F= 3.21; Sig 0.000) of the employees of Ministry of East African Community Affairs. To this effect, the null hypothesis that there is no significant difference between the prepotency of needs and reward valence of the employees of Ministry of East African Community Affairs is rejected and the acceptance of the alternative hypothesis to the effect that there is a positive and significant difference between prepotency of needs and reward valence.

Ho2: There is no significant relationship between the prepotency of needs and reward valence of the employees of Ministry of East African Community Affairs

Table 2: Correlation between the Prepotency of needs and reward valence among employees of Ministry of East African Community Affairs

		Prepotency of needs	Level of reward valence
PREPOTENCY OF NEEDS	Pearson’s correlation	1	.441 ^{xx}
	Sig. (2 tailed)	.236	.000
	N		236
LEVEL OF REWARD VALENCE	Pearson’s correlation	.441 ^{xx}	1
	Sig. (2 tailed)	.000	
	N	235	235

^{xx}. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2 tailed)

Using Pearson's linear correlation coefficient test, to test for the relationship if any, between prepotency of needs and level of reward valence among the employees of Ministry of East African Community Affairs, the results revealed a positive and significant relationship at the 0.05 level of significance (prepotency of needs $p = .441$ $r = .000$ and level of reward valence $p = .441$ $r = .000$). To this effect, the null hypothesis of no significant relationship between prepotency of needs and level of reward valence is rejected and the acceptance of the alternative hypothesis to the effect that there is a positive and significant relationship between prepotency of needs and the level of reward valence among the employees of Ministry of East African Community Affairs.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The study concludes that the respondents of the Ministry of the East sectors despite the potential for more financially lucrative careers in the private sector. African Community Affairs that took part in this study had their safety needs fairly influenced by the reward valence. This is certainly because of the Public Service Motivation theory which explains why some people choose careers in the government and non-profit Perry and Wise (1990) have argued that people with high Public Service Motivation (PSM) are more likely than others to choose government jobs, to perform better on the job, and to respond more to non- utilitarian incentives once in government.

In objective 3 shown on table 4.17 of the ministry of East African Community Affairs, the research dealt with finding out how belonging needs influence reward valence of employees of the ministry of East African Community Affairs, these are friendship, family, and sexual intimacy. The study found that this objective had a mean of 2.34 and this was interpreted as fair. Furthermore, based in the findings of this study, it was concluded that the respondents in this study had their belonging needs fairly met by the reward valence. This is confirmed by the level of reward valence which shows that many employees' expectations on reward should be commensurate with their efforts. This had a mean of 4.8, interpreted as satisfactory and ranked 5. Maicibi (2007) has stated that one of the general goals for rewarding employees is to motivate them. Rewards are intended to provide incentive to the employees to perform their work with willing and interest. With willingness the workers develop co-operative action, which is treasured most for realizing the organization goals. Thus, the employees of the Ministry of East African Community Affairs have their belonging needs according to Maslow's hierarchy of needs fairly rewarded by the management of the Ministry of East African Community Affairs.

The study also concludes that the respondents who participated in this study had their esteem needs fairly rewarded by the management of the East African Community Affairs according to Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs theory. This is supported by the level of reward valence of the respondents of the Ministry of East

African Community Affairs, which shows that each individual in the ministry thinks that the value of the reward meets the need for some esteem. This had a mean of 4.04, which was interpreted as satisfactory and ranked 6. The employees of the ministry were then motivated to perform better at their tasks. Koontz and Weirich have stated that motivation involves a chain reaction, starting out with felt needs

Finally, the respondents in this study from the Ministry of East African Community Affairs had their self-actualization needs influenced very unsatisfactorily by the reward valence. This finding is supported by Vroom (1990) who contended that the most important managerial implication emerging from Maslow's work is that most employees experience a variety of needs motivating them to come to work and perform at a given level of effort. It is important for a manager to consider employee unique profile of felt needs when explaining his/her response to the organization. Self-actualized persons have frequent occurrences of peak experience, which are energized moments of profound happiness and harmony. However, according to Maslow, only a small percentage of the population reaches the level of self-actualization. Therefore Maslow's hierarchy of Needs theory has been revalidated.

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